

PSYCHOLINGUISTIC ASPECTS OF COMPLEX SENTENCE FORMATION IN MODERN TURKISH AND AZERBAIJANI

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Abstract: *The study of complex structural models in modern Turkish and Azerbaijani from the perspective of communicative syntax reveals a number of noteworthy phenomena. These phenomena are not directly conditioned by the structural characteristics of the language itself; rather, they emerge primarily under the influence of extralinguistic factors. Such factors include the participants' attitude toward the topic of discussion and toward each other, the communicative intention pursued during the speech act, as well as the manipulative tactics and strategies employed by one or both interlocutors.*

Keywords: *modern Turkish, Azerbaijani, complex sentence models, psycholinguistics, communicative syntax, positive and negative manipulation*

Аннотация: *Изучение сложных структурных моделей в современном турецком и азербайджанском языках с позиции коммуникативного синтаксиса выявляет ряд примечательных явлений. Эти явления не обусловлены непосредственно структурными характеристиками самого языка, а формируются преимущественно под влиянием экстралингвистических факторов. К таким факторам относятся отношение участников общения к теме обсуждения и друг к другу, коммуникативное намерение, реализуемое в процессе речевого акта, а также манипулятивные тактики и стратегии, применяемые одним или обоими коммуникантами.*

Ключевые слова: *современный турецкий язык, азербайджанский язык, сложные модели предложений, психолингвистика, коммуникативный синтаксис, позитивная и негативная манипуляция*

Annotatsiya: *Zamonaviy turk va ozarbayjon tillarida murakkab strukturaviy modellarni kommunikativ sintaksis nuqtayi nazaridan o'rganish bir qator e'tiborga molik hodisalarni aniqlash imkonini beradi. Ushbu hodisalar bevosita tilning o'ziga xos struktur xususiyatlari bilan belgilanmaydi, balki asosan ekstralingvistik omillar ta'siri ostida yuzaga keladi. Bunday omillarga muloqot ishtirokchilarining muhokama mavzusiga va bir-biriga bo'lgan munosabati, nutq jarayonida ko'zlangan kommunikativ maqsad, shuningdek, suhbatdoshlarning biri yoki ikkalasi tomonidan qo'llaniladigan manipulyativ taktika va strategiyalar kiradi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *zamonaviy turk tili, ozarbayjon tili, murakkab gap modellari, psixolingvistika, kommunikativ sintaksis, ijobiy va salbiy manipulyatsiya*

The psycholinguistic analysis of complex sentence models in Turkish demonstrates that the information explicitly presented and the information implicitly inferred often do not coincide. This discrepancy, in turn, contributes to the “ballasting” of the Turkish sentence, increasing its volume and giving rise to a more complex construction. As noted by G. Abilova and K. Ashirkhanova, the regulation of sentence length may be directly conditioned by the communicative situation and guided by the interlocutors' communicative intentions and strategies (1, pp. 103–116).

According to A. M. Alparslan, applying traditional Indo-European syntactic criteria to the analysis of Turkish complex sentences, while at the same time treating the expanded simple sentence as a complex one, inevitably leads to research difficulties. Nevertheless, stylistic and semantic distinctions, as well as the choice of conjunctions, postpositions, and other auxiliary words involved in the verbal representation of events, can convey subtle semantic nuances (2). For example:

In Azerbaijani: *Mən sənə düşündüklərimi dedim, bundan sonra sənə qərarını gözləyəcəyəm* (“I told you what I thought; from now on, I will wait for your decision”) and *Mən sənə düşündüklərimi dedikdən sonra, sənə verdiyin qərarını gözləyəcəyəm* (“After telling you what I thought, I will wait for the decision you make”).

In Turkish: *Sana ne düşündüğümü söyledim, şimdi sənə qərarını bekleyəcəyim – Sana ne düşündüğümü söyledikten sonra, sənə qərarını bekleyəcəyim* (“I told you what I thought; now I will wait for your decision” – “After telling you what I thought, I will wait for your decision”).

In both cases, we are not simply confronted with structural differences. In these examples, we witness how the same deep sentence structure can be shaped differently according to distinct communicative intentions, as well as how it is conditioned by sufficiently different intensional factors (in terms of communicative purpose). Here, at first glance, we see the presentation of the same sentence both in a complex sentence format and in an expanded simple sentence model (expanded due to the inclusion of verbal connective elements). However, a deeper analysis reveals that, in the first pair of examples, the implicit expression of exhortation, warning, or implicit pressure is present. At least in this case, the first component of the complex sentence – the information provided in the initial simple sentence – is given in the subsequent sentence through informational comparison or constitutive (contextual-situational) contrast. In the second pair (in both languages, in the second sentence model), no implicit negativity or contrast is perceived.

This demonstrates that sometimes the presentation of the same sequence of actions in different sentence models may not affect the information in the deep layer of meaning, but it can influence its linguopragmatic and psycholinguistic presentation and comprehension. It should be recalled that, regardless of whether the presentation is in imperative or non-imperative form, the verbal expression of communicative intentions – such as request, persuasion, advice, encouragement, interdiction (prohibition), and similar – falls within the domain of psycholinguistic research (5, p. 46). Such phenomena have been investigated in several psycholinguistic studies within the framework of semantic syntax (for further details, see 3, pp. 38–40). These cases form the linguistic category known as conditionality, which, as L. Q. Khabibulina notes, manifests at the foundational level of cause-and-effect relations studied jointly by psychology, logic, and philosophy, and can be realized in the modality of the sentence (6, pp. 52–53).

Another noteworthy aspect concerns the conditional understanding of each other's ideas (in a figurative sense) by the participants, depending on their social distance and level of psychological contact, through hints or half-utterances. As V. P. Glukhov emphasizes, this is made possible by maximal simplification of syntax and the “absolute condensation” of ideas (4, p. 146). In other words, manipulative information such as threat, warning, or pressure can be presented not in an overt, extended form, but in a condensed and laconic manner.

“Evet, kızımız derdini söyledi söylemesine ama bakalım sonrası ne olacak” (7); “Ben söylemesine söyledim de duracak değilim” (8).

These sentences, according to Turkish complex sentence models, consist of two clauses and therefore correspond to the complex sentence standard. However, the semantic load and syntactic realization of these sentences are oriented toward verbalizing deeper meanings and psycholinguistic conditioning. At the subordinate level, the intensional motivation directed toward perspective (related to actions to be performed in the future) increases the semantic value and weight; on the other hand, the relevance of past events is minimized (*söyledi söylemesine; söylemesine söyledim*).

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